

Quantum Probabilistic Interactions and +p/-p Invariance Breaking

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In classical physics, a particle traveling to the right is the mirror image of one traveling to the left. In terms of a spatial density (the time spent in each constant dx), the value is the same, as is the energy. A similar notion of such a spatial invariance is in the classical conservation of energy equation for a bound particle: $p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E$.

Quantum mechanics seems to be different because $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are distinctly different spatial probabilities, i.e. they are dynamic. It is not just that case that a particle moves to the right for $\exp(ipx)$ and to the left for $\exp(-ipx)$. The impulse hit probabilities (represented by $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$) are distinctly different. If one wishes to create an OR situation and write: $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and use this in a conservation of energy equation, then simply including only positive or negative p values in $W(x)$ leads to a complex average kinetic energy $-1/2m \ d/dx \ dW/dx / W$ which cannot be used with $V(x)$ and E . Furthermore, W_- (only negative p) and W_+ (only positive p) values do not yield the same average kinetic energy. Fortunately, given that this is a statistical average for a localized object (somewhat analogous to a gas), one may combine $W_+ + W_-$ and obtain a real kinetic energy.

We have argued in previous notes that there exists a quantum-classical duality. For example, for a free particle one has two independent notions. One is $x=vt$ which describes the center-of-mass of the particle. We take this to represent a state description which treats v and $-v$ as mirror images. $\exp(ipx)$, on the other hand, represents probabilistic impulse hits and does not define the state by itself, we argue, only its interactions. Interactions are physical and define what happens in an interacting system. One may, however, measure a system, i.e. interact with $\exp(ipx)$, and this should define a measurement state (a second state ensemble average). For example, $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$ which is equivalent to the constant dt in each dx associated with $x=vt$. Thus, the two states coincide, but $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ means that one may place the 2-slit apparatus at any x point and is not about the center-of-mass, as $x=vt$ is.

In some cases, the two states are quite different. $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents an interaction state, but $v_{rms}(x)$ from $.5mv_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x) = -1/2m \ d/dx \ dW/dx / W$ represents a center-of-mass state description. (Note: in these cases a state means an average state, i.e. an average over many ensemble entries.)

If one takes $W^*(x)W(x)$ and integrates over x , then interference terms vanish and one obtains a classical counting of distinct p value states with their weight $a^*(p)a(p)$. This, we argue, leads to the notion of orthogonality of probabilities. In classical probability, there is no such notion, but there is the notion of AND (multiply) probabilities. Given $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, if one multiplies one removes p , i.e. the interactions and only sees the state left. $W^*(x)W(x)$ yields a set of peaks which represent a pattern of probabilistic hits in space which define a state which one would measure in space. The interference pattern, however, must be one such that if one integrates over x , one only obtains a classical sum of probabilities $a^*(p)a(p)$'s as mentioned above. This leads to the notion of orthogonal $\exp(ipx)$'s (which follows mathematically anyway). If one considers different bound E_n states, then these two are orthogonal because $W^{*n1}(x)W^{n2}(x)$ mean $n1$ and $n2$ are associated with different energies and integrating over x cannot show a result which looks like a state result, where $W^{*n}(x)W^n(x)$ shows a state result. In

order to achieve this orthogonality (linked directly to the notion of a state) one must have that $W_n(x)$ usually has 0 points and is positive and negative with the possible exception of a ground state. In other words, if $\int W_1^*(x)W_2(x) dx$ is not 0, one violates conservation of energy.

As a result, we argue an average probability for a bound state must statistically include +p and -p contributions and must create a function which has positive and negative peaks (except possibly for the ground state), i.e. $W(x)$ must have 0 points. This $W(x)$ is linked to a measurement state $W^*(x)W(x)$, but this is strictly considering $\exp(ipx)$ s. We argue that there are two pieces of information for a free particle, $x=vt$ and $\exp(ipx)$. There must also be an average state linked to $x=vt$ and this given by $KE_{ave}(x) = .5m v_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x) + V(x) = E$ which shows that the particle may exist and have average kinetic energy even at $W(x)=0$ points. When measuring a system, one interacts with the $\exp(ipx)$ s and so the $W^*(x)W(x)$ state is the one which is traditionally presented, but whether one measures the center-of-mass motion or not, one also has the notion of the $x=vt$, i.e. $v_{rms}(x)$ state (average) as well, we argue.

Quantum-Classical Interrelationship and the Notion of States

Traditionally, quantum mechanics is a statistical theory which is thought to yield deterministic Newtonian mechanics in the high energy limit. We argue, however, that quantum and classical ideas co-exist and that one must focus on both center-of-mass motion and interactions as governed differently. In particular, we argue that a free particle's center-of-mass moves classically (deterministically) as:

$$x=vt \quad ((1))$$

There is, however, a probability for an interaction to occur (either in t or x) given by

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((2))$$

If a particle moves without interacting, then $x=vt$ describes its state, but if it encounters a 2-slit apparatus, then $\exp(ipx)$ describes the probabilistic interactions. Given this interaction, one should solve for it probabilistically using $\exp(-ipx)$, but this begs the question: What is the state? Each time a photon or particle passes through the 2-slit apparatus, it moves as $x=vt$, but overall a pattern of detection/measurement is created on a screen far from the slits. This is also a state. The question is: How does one transition from a probability $\exp(ipx)$ to a state description?

We suggest that for a free particle, we have the center-of-mass state given by $x=vt$. If one takes:

$$\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1 \quad ((3))$$

$((3))$ describes a kind of frozen interaction state. $((3))$ is a little unusual. $\exp(ipx)$ means that the object (photon or particle) has a resolution of \hbar/p and can probabilistically interact with slits with roughly this separation or resolve objects separated by this distance. These are physical results and so what does a 1 value for every x mean? One might argue that it coincides with

$x=vt$ in that the same dt exists for each fixed dx . ((3)), however, is related to interaction and one should explain it using interaction ideas. Even though a resolution exists, the complex form of $\exp(ipx)$ means that the interaction is not preferred for any specific x . In particular, one could place a 2-slit apparatus at any x and observe the same average result. Thus, one has two state descriptions ((3)) and $x=vt$ and they coincide for the single free particle.

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$$

In many problems, one does not have a single free particle $\exp(ipx)$, but rather an OR situation given by:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \ ((4))$$

A common example is a single bound particle. We argued above that two states exist for a free particle namely $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ and $x=vt$. We note that even though $x=vt$ is directional, the statement:

The same dt is spent in each dx ((5)) is not.

In the bound case, an related statement is:

$$p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E \ ((6))$$

This holds for both $p(x)$ and $-p(x)$. A quantum statistical description of this problem should recognize that one has a trapped particle and so statistically over time both $-p$ and p are included. This leads to a $W(x)$ which includes both p and $-p$ and is a real function which allows one to write:

$$-1/2m \ d/dx \ dW/dx/W + V(x) = E_n \ ((7))$$

If one considers $x=vt$, one might argue that v changes at each x in ((6)), but E does not. The analogy with $x=vt$ seems to be based on energy because for $v=\text{constant}$, $E=\text{constant}$. This explains why $v(x)$ and $-v(x)$ are treated the same in terms of the same dt spent in a particular dx at x .

If one tries to break the spatial symmetry ($-p$, $+p$), then the quantum result becomes unusual because one has:

$$W_+ = \text{Sum over } p \geq 0 \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \ \text{and} \ W_- = \text{Sum over } p \leq 0 \ a(p)\exp(-ipx) \ ((8))$$

Neither of these yield a real kinetic energy which is a problem and the notion of W_+ , W_- breaks the idea of a bound state as an overall equilibrium localized state.

The question now becomes: What are the two states linked to $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ and $x=vt$?

We suggest that the first is:

$W^*(x)W(x)$ ((9)) which describes measurements, i.e. hit areas from the particle

If one integrates over dx , then one obtains $\sum_p a^*(p)a(p)$. Setting this integral to 1, yields $\sum_p a^*(p)a(p) = 1$. Thus, the form $W^*(x)W(x)$ is linked with classical particle counting, involves the orthogonality of $\exp(ipx)$ s, but at the same is associated with an ensemble average interaction pattern (a state) given by $W^*(x)W(x)$.

The second state, linked to $x=vt$, is given by:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = .5m v_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W \quad ((10))$$

The two states again appear.

Orthogonality

It is well-known that quantum eigenstates are orthogonal (say in space). This, however, is a math statement. It means directly that in the single particle quantum case for a real $W(x)$, that $W(x)$ has 0 points (except possibly for the ground state). As a result, $W(x)$ cannot represent the full state of the quantum system (as it is sometimes presented). We saw in the above section that there are two states, $W^*(x)W(x)$ and $v_{rms}(x)$. If $W^*(x)W(x)=0$, this means that there are no measurement hits at $W(x)=0$, but $v_{rms}(x)$ is non-zero at such a point, meaning that the particle is still there (in the ensemble average). One might ask: Why should $W(x)$, a physical impulse hit probability pattern arrange itself in order to create 0 points. We argue that this answer is linked to the notion of state. If one has $W_{n1}(x)$ and $W_{n2}(x)$, these are different states because they have different physical average energies. One must have:

$$\int W_{n1}^*(x)W_{n2}(x) dx = 0 \quad \text{by conservation of energy} \quad ((11))$$

One may use $\int W^*(x)W(x) dx = 1$ to find $\sum_p a^*(p)a(p) = 1$, but ((11)) cannot yield any result as such a result (nonzero) would violate conservation of energy. For a real $W_{n1}(x)$, this means that one must have positive and negative peaks and 0 points (except for the ground state). As a result, two ensemble average states are created. One is linked with $v_{rms}(x)$ and conservation of energy, but the second is linked with impulse hits which creates its own measurement state $W^*(x)W(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a quantum particle is associated with a classical $x=vt$ and an interaction probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. One either considers an interaction in time or x . We further suggest that these two pieces are associated with two states. $x=vt$ means that a particle spends the same dt in each dx (whether it moves to the right or left). This is akin to each particle $-v$ or v having the same energy. The second state is given by $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$ which means that the

particle may interact with a 2-slit apparatus at any x point with no preference. As a result, these two states seem to coincide for a single free particle.

In a single particle bound case, matters are more complicated. There exists an OR situation, $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. $W^*(x)W(x)$ gives a measurement state, but this is not the full picture. $\psi_{rms}(x)$ from $\frac{1}{2}m v_{rms}(x) v_{rms}(x) = -\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ gives a second state (linked to the $x=vt$ notion). It is important to have both ensemble average states, because $W(x)$ means $W^*(x)W(x)=0$, $\psi_{rms}(x) \neq 0$. The particle's center-of-mass still exists and moves at $x=0$, one just does not have interactions at this point.

The existence of the interaction state $W^*(x)W(x)$ is also linked to particle counting because integrating over dx and setting this equal to 1 yields $\sum_p a^*(p)a(p)=1$. We argue that this means that $\int W^*_{n1}(x)W_{n2}(x)dx=0$ because of conservation of energy. $W_{n1}(x)$ must adjust itself to create the necessary zero points needed to make $W_{n1}(x)$ orthogonal to other $W_n(x)$'s, but at the same time create the second state: $\frac{1}{2}m v_{rms}(x) v_{rms}(x) = -\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ such that $KE_{ave}(x)+V(x)=E_n$.